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First dissemination event

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Introduction

The present deliverable was meant to report the development and outcomes of the *first dissemination event*, aimed at presenting to a broad public the first prototype of the MHMD system and relevant project developments. This event, however, has been planned for M20, where the *EU Digital Assembly (Sofia, 25-26 June 2018)*, co-organised by the European Commission and the Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union around the themes of EU digital policy, offered the ideal context for this presentation, at the presence of the relevant stakeholder communities, including industry, SMEs and policy makers. The report will thus detail the demo that has been planned for the upcoming event, while its outcomes will be the object of subsequent relevant deliverables (e.g., D10.7).

This event has not been, though, the only occasion where the project has been showcased. In this first reporting period, the Consortium has been in fact engaged in a thick agenda of public events in the domain of health IT, personal data, AI, blockchain and ICT for health, either organised at institutional level (e.g., *eHealth Week*), by industry (e.g., *HIMSS*) or by public initiatives in the personal data ecosystem (e.g., *MyData*), with different publics and putting in relevance different aspects and implications. The D10.3 deliverable reports therefore on the contents and outcomes of these diversified dissemination opportunities, where the Project Coordinator and other Consortium partners have successfully presented the project in front of relevant academic community, private sector stakeholders or institutions and policy makers, chaired and animated sessions on relevant themes (e.g., personal data, health data, blockchain in health, ICT for health), and created fruitful cross-fertilisation and collaboration opportunities with members of research institutions, private companies, associations and other EU-funded initiatives.

1 Dissemination events (M1-M19)

1.1 Dissemination events in Y1 (M1-M12)

1.1.1 HDI Day

HEALTHCARE
DATA INSTITUTE

When	17 November 2016	Where	Paris, France	Venue	Healthcare Data Institute
Details	Public annual event where HDI members meet the public around a presentation of the Think Tank's work, keynote presentations and round tables				
Organisers	Healthcare Data Institute (HDI)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Participation and networking				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, industry and SME		
Event material	-				

1.1.2 BDVA Valencia Summit 2016

When	30 November – 2 December 2016	Where	Valencia, Spain
Theme	<i>Big Data driving business</i>		
Details	BDVA summits are meeting occasions between Big Data players in Europe to influence the development of the European Big Data Ecosystem.		
Organisers	Big Data Value Association (BDVA)	Venue	Ciudad Politécnica de la Innovación (CPI), Universitat Politècnica de Valencia
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher and Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus		
What	Public project presentation within <i>Data Protection and Privacy-preserving Big Data Technology</i> session		
Dissemination	Website , twitter, facebook	Public	Industry, academia, public administration, data owners and users
Event material	Website (1) and (2) , handbook		

1.1.3 Information and Networking Days on H2020 Big Data PPP topics 2017

European Commission

When	17-18 January 2017	Where	Luxembourg	Venue	European Convention Center Luxembourg - Luxembourg Congrès
Details	Public event directed to inform and guide potential applicants preparing project proposals and facilitate sharing of ideas and experiences, giving participants the chance to network and to find partners for their projects, and presenting objectives and roadmap of the first <i>Big Data Public-Private Partnership (PPP)</i> projects issued from the 2016 call for proposals				
Organisers	European Commission				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher and Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Public project presentation within <i>Big Data PPP call ICT-18 (Privacy-preserving big data technologies)</i> session, start of networking activities with the Coordination and Support Action of the Big Data PPP call ICT-18, with the mandate to explore the societal and ethical implications and provide a broad basis and wider context to validate privacy-preserving technologies				
Dissemination	Website	Public	EU institutional representatives, members of other Consortia		
Event material	Website				

1.1.4 First United Nations' ITU Workshop on "Security Aspects of Blockchain"

When	21 March 2017	Where	Geneva, Switzerland	Venue	-
Details	Workshop dedicated to blockchain technology and its implication to security, particularly evaluating the current status of blockchain technology and its maturity, as well as discussing relevant open issues including security and privacy aspects related to blockchain applications and possible means for extending on-line trust using blockchain technologies, as a platform to share findings and for dialogue on policy and regulatory implications of blockchain between enterprises working on blockchain applications and regulators from various industrial-/economic sectors				
Organisers	International Telecommunication Union (ITU)				
Who	David Manset, Gnùbila				
What	Public presentation of MHMD, participation and networking				
Dissemination	<u>Website</u> , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, policy makers and regulators		
Event material	-				

1.1.5 EDBT/ICDT 2017 Joint Conference

When	21-24 March 2017	Where	Venice, Italy	Venue	Congress Center of the San Servolo Island
Details	Joint 20th International Conference on Extending Database Technology (EDBT, an established and prestigious forum for the exchange of the latest research results in data management) and 20th International Conference on Database Theory (ICDT, a scientific conference on research on the foundations of database systems)				
Organisers	International Conference on Extending Database Technology (EDBT), International Conference on Database Theory (ICDT)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus	What	Paper for the session on “Big Data Management Challenges and Solutions in the Context of European Projects”		
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia		
Event material	Website				

1.1.6 Smart Contracts Day

When	31 March 2017	Where	Athens, Greece	Venue	Divani Caravel hotel
Details	A single day in which expert speakers presented talks on the topic of Information, Privacy and Smart Contracts in the interdisciplinary field merging Cryptography and Law.				
Organisers	Cryptography and Security Laboratory, University of Athens				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus Harry Dimitropoulos and Omiros Metaxas, Athena RC	What	Participation and networking		
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia		
Event material	Website , blog article				

1.1.7 RDA 9th Plenary Meeting

When	5-7 April 2017	Where	Barcelona, Spain	Venue	Barcelo Sants Hotel
Theme	<i>Data Infrastructures for Open Science</i>				
Details	RDA Plenaries are biannual events, held in different places around the world, which bring together data scientists, librarians, computer scientists, and domain scientists with the goal of creating tangible deliverables that improve data sharing across disciplines, technologies, and countries.				
Organisers	Barcelona Supercomputing Center-Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS), Research Data Alliance Europe (RDA-Europe)				
Who	Edwin Morley Fletcher, Mirko De Maldè and Ludovica Durst, Lynkeus, Rocco Panetta, P&A, and Aggelos Kiayias, Athena RC				
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to a <i>Joint IG Big Data and IG Health Data Topics Exploration Meeting</i> focused on big health datasets and privacy and security issues. • Chair of the <i>IG Health Data Meeting</i>, entitled <i>Meaningful Health Data for Research and for Industry</i>, on assessing the differences between US, Australia and EU regulation of health data, mapping existing practical policies, relevant projects, and experiences related to health data, identifying other groups' activities, and considering the value of industry participation in health data and discussing how to engage partners from industry in the HD-IG. • Chair the of <i>Health Data and Blockchain BoF Meeting</i>, entitled <i>Making use of Blockchain in dealing with Health Data</i>, exploring public and private initiatives in Europe and US addressing the potential of applying the blockchain approach to health data (with <i>presentation of MHMD</i> and of the <i>blockchain</i>) and evaluating the opportunity of establishing a working group on <i>Blockchain in health data</i> to debate its potential and whether the blockchain can ensure compliance with advanced data protection requirements (i.e., GDPR). 				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry		
Event material	Website				

1.1.8 eHealth Week 2017

When	10-12 May 2017	Where	St. Julian's, Malta	Venue	-
Organisers	European Commission, HIMSS Europe, Maltese Ministry of Health as part of their Presidency of the Council of the European Union, World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe (WHO/Europe)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher and Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Two public project presentations: 1) <i>The Blockchain-centred approach of MyHealthMyData</i> , within the session "Healthcare: New Kids on the Blockchain"; 2) <i>MHMD</i> , within the Italian Community Session on <i>Patient Data and the GDPR – How should I manage the Data?</i> , dealing with how to address the incoming issues of defining clear guidelines and reference practices at the national and regional level for managing health data in compliance with the new EU privacy regulation (GDPR).				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Industry, academia, public administration		
Event material	-				

1.1.9 1st Joint EU Blockchain Conference

When	11 May 2017	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	European Parliament
Theme	<i>Spotlight on Blockchain: a new generation of digital services</i>				
Details	Public meeting to discuss challenges and potential application of the blockchain technology				
Organisers	European Commission, European Parliament				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus David Manset, gnùbila				
What	Participation and networking				
Dissemination	-	Public	Public administration, industry, academia		
Event material	Website				

1.1.10 RDA meets Nordic researchers

When	14 June 2017	Where	Goteborg, Sweden	Venue	Chalmers Teknikpark
Details	Yearly meeting with the Nordic research data community, including researchers, policy makers in open access to data, open science enablers and re-use of research data champions to join and discuss technological and sociological matters around the re-use of research data on the national, Nordic, European and global level				
Organisers	Research Data Alliance (RDA) Europe				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation of MHMD				
Dissemination	-	Public	Industry, academia, public administration		
Event material	Website				

1.1.11 CTIE and Infrachain

When	16 June 2017	Where	Luxembourg	Venue	CTIE
Organisers	The Centre des technologies de l'Etat (CTIE), Infrachain a.s.b.l., the company incorporated by the top players in the Luxembourg Blockchain scene, supported by the Luxembourg government				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation of MHMD				
Dissemination	-	Public	Industry, academia, public administration		
Event material	-				

1.1.12 EHRA EUROPACE-CARDIOSTIM Congress

EUROPACE
EHRA 2017
 18-21 June
 CARDIOSTIM Vienna, Austria

When	18-20 June 2017	Where	Vienna, Austria	Venue	-
Details	Annual congress discussing latest discoveries in the field of arrhythmias				
Organisers	European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA), European Society of Cardiology (ESC)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation of MHMD within a talk on "Deriving clinically relevant information from big data"				
Dissemination	-	Public	Clinicians, academia		
Event material	Programme				

1.1.13 Athens eHealth: Digital Health Meetup

When	6 July 2017	Where	Athens, Greece	Venue	Athens Chamber of Commerce & Industry (EBEA)
Details	eHealth and Health IT stakeholders get together every month to chat, to debate, to network, to ask questions, to learn, to exchange information and discover opportunities.				
Organisers	eHealth Forum Team				
Who	Omiros Metaxas, Athena RC				
What	Presentation "Knowing me, knowing you, knowing your disease: A new paradigm in healthcare privacy-preserving data sharing and big data analytics"				
Dissemination	-	Public	Clinicians, patients, caretakers, medical students and citizens		
Event material	Meetup page (1) and (2) , Facebook page				

1.1.14 MyData 2017

When	30 August – 1 September 2017	Where	Tallinn, Estonia Helsinki, Finland	Venue	Tallinn University Conference Centre Helsinki Hall Of Culture
Theme	Advancing Human Centric Personal Data				
Details	The MyData conference takes dialogue and collective action across the whole spectrum of expertise in data research and management, including business, legal, tech, and social, to implement the vision of a fair digital society, where only ethically sound approaches to personal data can bring value and wellbeing to citizens, businesses, governments, and civil society				
Organisers	Open Knowledge, Aalto University, Fing and Tallinn University				
Who	Anna Rizzo, Lynkeus Julian Ranger and Daniel Bayley, digi.me				
What	Public project presentation within <i>Topic Track 3, CASE STUDIES</i> , focused on the actual and future services to be generated by the personal data model				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook, MHMD brochure	Public	Industry, SME, academia, public administration		
Event material	Website				

1.1.15 RDA 10th Plenary Meeting

When	19-21 September 2017	Where	Montréal, Canada	Venue	Centre Mont-Royal
Theme	<i>Better Data, Better Decisions</i>				
Organisers	Université de Montréal, Research Data Canada, Research Data Alliance (RDA)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher and Ludovica Durst, Lynkeus David Manset, gnùbila				
What	Chair of the IG Health Data session: <i>Health data mapping and diverging trends in health data protection</i> Chair of the BoF on Health Data and Blockchain and presentations by Edwin Morley-Fletcher and David Manset on <i>Making use of Blockchain in dealing with Health Data</i> .				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, SMEs		
Event material	Website				

1.1.16 i~HD & EMIF joint conference 2017

**Realising the Value from Health Data ~
Improving Care and Research**

JOINT EVENT

The European Institute For
Innovation Through Health Data

EMIF

**September 21-22, 2017
MADRID, SPAIN**

i+12
Instituto de Investigación
Hospital 12 de Octubre

i~HD Annual Conference 2017

When	21-22 September 2017	Where	Madrid, Spain	Venue	Healthcare Research Institute of Hospital Universitario 12 de Octubre
Theme	<i>Realising the Value from Health Data for Improving Care and Research</i>				
Details	Public meeting directed to guide and catalyse the quality, interoperability and trustworthy uses of health data for optimising health and knowledge discovery				
Organisers	European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD), European Medical Information Framework (EMIF) project, funded by Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI)				
Who	Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Participation and networking activity				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, SME, representatives of the Spanish Ministry, European Commission, patient associations, health insurers, policymakers, clinical research and pharma industry		
Event material	Website (1) (2)				

1.1.17 eHealth Tallinn

Organised by: Supported by: @eHealthTallinn #eHealthTallinn www.ehealthtallinn2017.ee

When	16-18 October 2017	Where	Tallinn, Estonia	Venue	Creative Hub Tallinn (Kultuurikatel)
Theme	<i>Health in the Digital Society. Digital Society for Health</i>				
Details	The high-level conference addressed how digital technologies and the wider use of health data are changing our lives and the ways of healthcare, through a combination of educational sessions, interactive workshops and networking opportunities, to showcase already existing digital health solutions as well as use-cases and technologies for citizen-centric health services and systems				
Organisers	Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs (as part of Estonia’s Presidency of the Council of the European Union), ECHAAlliance and HIMSS Europe				
Who	Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Chair of <i>Blockchain: Unleashing the Power of Free-Flowing Data</i> session (including presentation with introduction to the theme, speakers and mention to MHMD) Participation and networking activity				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, SME, patient associations, policymakers		
Event material	Website				

BLOCKCHAIN: NEW WAYS TO MAKE THE DATA FLOWING?

- Blockchain ledger is the secure, non-editable record
- Stakeholder are equipped with a ‘wallet’ containing:
 - An encrypted identifier
 - His/her Dynamic Consent
 - His/her Data Access policy file
- This could lead to **Personal storage clouds** for ubiquitous individual data access through blockchain and advanced personal use.

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1.1.18 Stakeholder Workshop on GDPR Implementation and Health Data

When	23 October 2017	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	Albert Borschette Congress Center (CCAB)
Details	Stakeholder Workshop on GDPR Implementation and Health Data				
Organisers	European Commission				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus, Rocco Panetta, P&A, David Manset and Aurélie Bayle, Gnùbila				
What	Participation and networking				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, industry, SME, policymakers		
Event material	-				

1.2 Dissemination events in Y2 (M13-M18)

1.2.1 12th Forum on Risk Management in Health

When	29 November 2017	Where	Florence, Italy	Venue	Fortezza da Basso
Details	Forum Risk Management in Health is an annual event that reviews the technologies applied to patient safety. The Forum is a venue and opportunity for a debate on things to do for innovating and reforming the health system and make it more efficient and able to respond to the health needs of citizens.				
Organisers	Forum on Risk Management in Health				
Who	Edwin Morley Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation on <i>In-Silico medicine in Europe</i> with mention to MHMD, participation and networking				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, industry, political institutions		
Event material	-				

1.2.2 European Big Data Value Forum

When	21-23 November 2017	Where	Versailles, France	Venue	Palais des Congrès
Theme	<i>Trusted AI in Smart Industry</i>				
Details	The event covers cutting-edge industrial applications of Big Data technologies and innovative business cases of the data economy, inspiring future visions, and insights on EU policy-making and R&D&I funding in the area				
Organisers	European Data Forum (EDF), Big Data Value Association (BDVA), European Commission				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Chair of <i>Towards Privacy-Preserving Big Data</i> panel, with presentation of MHMD				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, SME, policymakers		

Event material -

1.2.3 EMA Data Anonymisation Workshop

When	30 November – 1 December 2017	Where	London, United Kingdom	Venue	European Medicines Agency (EMA)
Theme	<i>Data anonymisation - a key enabler for clinical data sharing</i>				
Details	The workshop aims to propose guiding principles to enable international data sharing in the public interest, to review anonymisation approaches applicable to a broader set of data which ensure privacy protection and meet the standards required to maintain accessibility and the scientific utility of data, and to examine opportunities for harmonisation of international clinical data sharing, taking into consideration data protection in the different jurisdictions				
Topics	Clinical trial data including individual patient level data and real-world data in the context of patient registries and individual cohort studies				
Organisers	European Medicines Agency (EMA), Multi-Regional Clinical Trials Center of Harvard and Brigham and Women’s Hospital (MRCT Center)				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Keynote lecture on “Encryption and Anonymisation in the age of artificial intelligence”				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, industry, SME, policymakers		
Event material	Programme				

1.2.4 RDA EU Data Innovation Forum

When	30 January 2018	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	The Hotel Brussels
Details	The goal of the event has been to collect and converge the different perspectives and push forward new innovative ideas in the overall context of the challenges and opportunities of the European Data Economy and data-driven innovation in Europe mapped to ongoing activities or future challenges to be addressed by RDA WGs & IGs. It also aimed to define a pragmatic list of data challenges to be discussed on a national level to influence the digital national agendas, or form proposals to be further discussed within the next RDA Plenaries				
Topics	The role of research data in the Data Economy context and the RDA contribution to the different Data Economy building blocks				
Organisers	Research Data Alliance (RDA) Europe				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Panel on “Short Introduction of blockchain and its possible role in IoT data trading” and presentation of MHMD by Edwin Morley-Fletcher				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, industry, SME, policymakers		
Event material	Website , Report				

1.2.5 EIP AHA Conference of Partners 2018

When	27 February 2018	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	European Parliament
Details	European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing Conference of Partners 2018				
Theme	<i>Digital transformation of health and care for Active and Healthy Ageing in Europe</i>				
Details	A working 2-day meeting, open to EIP on AHA partners and dedicated to reviewing the action plans of the Action Groups and the Reference Sites Collaborative Network, and especially how these plans are aligned with the European Commission policy activities, notably the "Transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market" Communication currently in preparation.				
Organisers	European Commission				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation of MHMD				
Dissemination	Twitter , Facebook	Public	EIP on AHA partners		
Event material	Website , streaming , programme				

EIP AHA - CONFERENCE OF PARTNERS 2018

2018-02-27 | 08:30 to 18:30 |

Recorded

MyHealthMyData (MHMD)

- MyHealthMyData guarantees privacy and security of healthcare data by:
 - having recourse to a distributed architecture based on **Blockchain** and **Smart Contracts**,
 - joining both clinical institutions as well as individuals making use of **Personal Data Accounts**.
- MHMD classifies sensitive data based on their **medical** as well as **predictive**, and **potentially economic**, value, aiming to:
 - assess the most suitable and robust de-identification and **encryption** technologies needed to preserve different types of information,
 - allow **advanced analytics** applied on such data,
 - evaluate the overall reliability of a generic multi-modular architecture.
- MHMD analyses users' behavioural patterns alongside ethical and cultural orientations, to identify dynamics related to events like **transparency**, the opening into force of the **GDPR**, and the interrelations of **hospitals** and **individuals** within a system like MHMD.
- MHMD checks the ability of avoiding privacy & security breaches by having recourse to:
 - **in-the-wild** testing,
 - public challenges of **penetration testing** and **vulnerability assessment**,
 - testing **optimal de-identification possibilities** on patients consenting to being used as test cases.
- MHMD ultimately aims to:
 - improve the design of **data-driven** (secondary) platforms,
 - foster the development of an **informative** enabled platform, in which a growing number of clinical institutions may find **secure GDPR compliant ways of sharing data** and leverage their value, as well as individuals, becoming able to easily access their personal data and control what use is made of them.

1.2.6 EIH High-Level Symposium "Insuring a healthy health: The winning model"

When	9 March 2018	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	European Parliament
Theme	<i>Insuring a Healthy Health: The Winning Model</i>				
Details	Symposium dedicated to exploring different aspects of the relationship between the changes affecting the healthcare industry and Insurance				
Organisers	European Institute for Health (EIH)				
Who	David Manset, gnùbila				
What	On behalf of the European Federation of Cybersecurity Experts, public presentation of the MHMD blockchain model				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter , Facebook	Public	Players from the "Insurance" ecosystem, industry stakeholders and EU institutions policy-makers, representatives from the cyber security sector		
Event material	Website , Event page , LinkedIn , Facebook				

1.2.7 Wired Health

When	15 March 2018	Where	Milan, Italy	Venue	Milano BASE cultural centre
Theme	<i>Innovation for life</i> (translated from Italian, <i>Innovazione per la vita</i>)				
Details	Organised within the <i>Milano Digital Week</i> , the event explored a wide range of topics in the domain of information and computer technology (ICT) applied to healthcare: how technology is changing medicine, what are the most recent developments of robotics for health, whether artificial intelligence (AI) could speed up diagnosis or blockchain better protect patient data, as well as most relevant trends at the intersection of medicine, digital technologies and new lifestyles				
Organisers	Wired magazine, HUMANITAS Research Hospital				
Who	Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation on the topic <i>How blockchain can be a valuable tool for safeguard patients' privacy</i> , including mention to MHMD				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	Academia, clinicians, policy makers, industry, SME		
Event material	Articles (1 – event showcase) and (2 – event programme) on Wired magazine				

1.2.8 World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS) Forum

When	19-23 March 2018	Where	Geneva, Switzerland	Venue	Milano BASE cultural centre
Theme	<i>Leveraging ICTs to Build Information and Knowledge Societies for Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)</i>				
Details	The World Summit on the Information Society Forum (WSIS) 2018 represents the world's largest annual gathering of the 'ICT for development' community. The event constitutes a global multi-stakeholder platform to explore the role of ICTs to facilitate the implementation of the WSIS Action Lines for advancing sustainable development goals and targets				
Organisers	International Telecommunication Union (ITU), UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), UN Development Program (UNDP), UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD)				
Who	David Manset, Gnùbila				
What	Panel presentation on the topic <i>Blockchain as an enabler of security and trust</i> , with mention to MHMD				
Dissemination	Twitter , Facebook	Public	Academia, clinicians, policy makers, industry, SME		
Event material	Website				

1.2.9 Towards a Health Research and Innovation Cloud – Challenges and Opportunities

When	13 March 2018	Where	Brussels	Venue	-
Organisers	Health Directorate of DG RTD				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Presentation of MHMD and co-chair, together with Caroline Gans-Combe, of the session on Ethics, legal and organisational challenges.				
Dissemination	-	Public	EU institutional representatives, industry and SME		
Event material	-				

1.2.10 RDA 11TH Plenary Meeting

When	21-23 March 2018	Where	Berlin, Germany	Venue	Helmholtz-Centre Potsdam
Theme	<i>From Data to Knowledge</i>				
Details	RDA Plenaries provide a forum to discuss the opportunities and challenges of a global data ecosystem of best practices, standards and interoperable data infrastructures fostering cross-disciplinary knowledge and innovation				
Organisers	Research Data Alliance (RDA) Europe, Helmholtz-Centre Potsdam - GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Helmholtz				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Mirko De Maldè and Ludovica Durst, Lynkeus David Manset, Gnùbila				
What	Chair of <i>Health Data Interest Group</i> and <i>Blockchain Applications in Health Working Group</i>				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter , Facebook	Public	Academia, policy makers, industry, SME		
Event material	Website				

1.2.11 Digital Day 2018

When	10 April 2018	Where	Brussels, Belgium	Venue	Square – Brussels Meeting Centre
Topics	Artificial intelligence, blockchain and health				
Details	The one-day event brought together high-level stakeholders in the fields of digital technology and telecommunication, to reach joint commitments for the digital future of Europe, in view of encouraging investment in European digital technologies and infrastructures, contributing to a competitive and socially secure society, better public services and security				
Organisers	European Commission, Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union				
Who	Edwin Morley Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Public presentation of MHMD, participation and networking				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter , Facebook	Public	European Commission, representatives of Member States and high-level stakeholder in the fields of digital technology and telecommunication upon invitation		
Event material	Website , factsheet on MHMD produced by the European Commission				

1.2.12 IBM MEDICEN

When	13 April 2018	Where	Paris, France	Venue	IBM France
Theme	<i>Blockchain for healthcare transformation</i>				
Details	The Paris Region competitiveness cluster Medicen Paris Region, in partnership with IBM France, organised the awareness seminar dedicated to the Blockchain and its Health applications. The program of the event included a plenary sessions, round tables and presentation of use cases, which aimed at making attendees understating the issues of the Blockchain, and its impacts for the health sector.				
Organisers	Medicen Paris Region				
Who	David Manset, Gnùbila				
What	Public presentation of MHMD as an innovative GDPR-compliant blockchain model for personal sensitive data sharing and value-based care				
Dissemination	Twitter	Public	Clinicians, industry and SME		
Event material	-				

1.2.13 eHealth2018

eHealth2018
12th Annual Conference on Health Informatics meets eHealth
8.-9. May 2018, Schönbrunn Palace, Vienna, Austria

SAVE THE DATE

When	8-9 May 2018	Where	Vienna, Austria	Venue	Schonbrunn Palace
Theme	12th Annual Conference on Health Informatics meets eHealth				
Details	The event provides a platform for researchers, practitioners, decision makers and vendors to discuss innovative health informatics and eHealth solutions so as to improve the quality and efficiency of health care.				
Organisers	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), the Austrian Working Group of Health Informatics and eHealth				
Who	Peter Kieseberg, SBA				
What	Presentation on the theme "Trusted data sharing enabled by blockchain technology", with mention to MHMD				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, clinicians, decision makers		
Event material	Website				

MY HEALTH MY DATA
Trusted data sharing enabled by blockchain technology

Peter Kieseberg (& Rudolf Mayer) SBA Research

MyHealthMyData at a glance

- Duration: November 2016 – October 2019
- 9 Research Partners: LYNKEUS, digi.me, HMC, gnúbila, Hes SO//GENE, TRANSFORMA, ATHENA
- 4 Clinical partners: CHARITÉ, Bambino Gesù, Queen Mary, IITC
- 1 Legal consultancy: PASCALLE ASSOCIATI
- 1 Industry: SIEMENS Healthineers

1.3 Upcoming (M19)

1.3.1 Big Data Value Meet-up Sofia

When	14-16 May 2018	Where	Sofia, Bulgaria	Venue	-
Topics	Digital health, ICT for health				
Details	The event has the twofold objective of strengthening collaborations among community members and increasing the visibility and awareness about the PPP in East Europe in general and Bulgaria in particular				
Organisers	Big Data Value Association				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Presentation of the progress status of MHMD, presentation and networking				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	Industry and SME, policy makers		
Event material	Website				

1.3.2 HIMSS Europe Conference and Exhibition 2018

When	27-29 May 2018	Where	Sitges, Spain	Venue	Melia Hotel
Topics	Digital health, ICT for health				
Details	The joint HIMSS Europe and Health 2.0 aims to gather digital health professionals from Europe and overseas to explore international innovations in consumer health, patient care, digital healthcare technologies, big data and analytics, AI and wearable tech, to initiate meaningful conversations and to create digital health marketplaces				
Organisers	HIMSS Europe				
Who	Mirko DE Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker within two sessions: <i>Playing with blockchain</i> , giving an introduction to the blockchain technology through a puzzle game, and <i>Personal Health Record (PHR) initiative session "Empowering Patients and Citizens to Become CEOs of their Own Health"</i> , with presentation of MHMD, exploring the emerging landscape of personal health record initiatives, particularly what they promise and how are they delivering on those promises				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	Clinicians, industry and SME, policy makers, patients associations		
Event material	Website				

2 Meetings with interested entities and authorities (M1-M19)

When	Where	Who	What
9 November 2016	Argonay, France	David Manset, Gnùbila	Meeting with the <i>European Parliament Vice-President and MPE, Sylvie Guillaume</i> , visiting the Haute-Savoie region
26 June 2017	Brussels, Belgium	David Manset, Gnùbila	Meeting with <i>Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT)</i>
27 July 2017	Rome, Italy	Rocco Panetta and Lorenzo Cristofaro, Panetta & Associati, Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus	Meeting with <i>F. Modafferi, Director of the Department "Public Liberty Rights and Health"</i> within the Italian Data Protection Authority ¹ , organised by Panetta & Associati
23 August 2017	Reykjavik, Iceland	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus	<i>Dattacalabs</i> met Edwin Morley-Fletcher and organised also a first meeting with the <i>Head of the Iceland Department of Health, Ing. Steinar Ingason</i> , within the <i>Directorate of Health, Embaetti Landlaeknis</i> . Other meetings followed, with the <i>SMEs TM Software and Reon. Dattacalabs</i> , having been recommended by <i>digi.me</i> as an experienced company with a significant track-record of work performed with government entities in the area of innovative services in health and IT, and more generally leveraging the personal data economy, and specifically supporting <i>digi.me</i> in its Icelandic extension, eventually agreed to provide MHMD with health datasets, coming both from <i>digi.me</i> Personal Data Accounts as well as from the national hospital in Reykjavik.
12 March 2018	Brussels, Belgium	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus	Meeting on MHMD at DG Connect with Ilias Iakovidis, Benoit Abeloos, Chiara Mazzone, and Pierre Marro
9 April 2018	Brussels, Belgium	David Manset, Gnùbila	Meeting of Be-Ys (which has purchased Gnùbila) with Mariya Gabriel, European Commissioner for Digital Economy and Society (see photo below)

¹ www.gpdp.it

3 First MHMD system demo: *Digital Assembly 2018* (M20)

When	25-26 June 2018	Where	Sofia, Bulgaria	Venue	National Palace of Culture
Topics	Digital transformation in Europe				
Details	The event represents a forum for stakeholders to debate, take stock and look ahead at how Europe and its partners around the world are preparing for the main digital policy challenges ahead, and offers the opportunity for dialogue on their potential benefits for citizens and businesses				
Organisers	European Commission, Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	EU member state representatives and policy makers upon invitation		
Event material	Website				

Materials for project showcase

Screens (2)

1. One video in loop about previous projects in ICT for health
2. One videos in loop showing overview of MHMD and other technical information, plus other relevant topics, such as WannaCry cyber-attack and GDPR regulation.

Posters (5)

1. One *general overview* of MHMD
2. One schematic illustration of *blockchain architecture*, with data workflows explained
3. One preview of the MHMD *user Interface* for the different use cases
4. One overview of *healthcare analytics* for anonymised data under development

5. One overview of *GDPR* and how MHMD has reached full compliance in regard to its different aspects

Demos (4)

1. One demo showing *techniques for automatic classification, encryption and encoding* of different types of data (e.g., pseudo & anonymisation, privacy impact assessment, etc.)
2. One demo of the *Data Catalogue*
3. One demo of the MHMD *User Interface* along with its four different use cases:
 - a. *individual register data* (in the app): login, connect to digi.me, select permissions, upload
 - b. *hospital register data* (in the website): what types of data will be released
 - c. *researcher consumer data* (website)
 - d. *pharma consumer data* (website)
4. Demo of different types of *healthcare analytics* under development

Attendants from Consortium

Partner	Members	Topic of expertise
Lynkeus	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Mirko De Maldè, Anna Rizzo, Ludovica Durst	<i>General aspects and coordination</i>
Gnùbila	David Manset	<i>Blockchain architecture</i>
HWC	Daniel Essafi	<i>User Interface and relevant use cases</i>
Athena RC	Minos Garofalakis	<i>Anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques</i>
HES-SO	Douglas Teodoro, Patrick Ruch	<i>Data catalogue</i>
P&A	Lorenzo Cristofaro	<i>GDPR compliance</i>
SBA	Rudolf Mayer	<i>Hacking challenge</i>
Siemens	Martin Kraus	<i>Healthcare analytics</i>
QMUL	Steffen Petersen, Aaron Lee	<i>Hospital engagement and role</i>